

Paper 3

**A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON
SCHOOL EDUCATION IN UDUP DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

Study of the Impact of Covid-19 on School education of Udupi district The Covid -19 impacts was everywhere, which resulted in the closure of schools and other educational institutions. This study aims to understand teachers' ability to adapt in to new normal educational context and their digital literacy to carry out school activities. This is a design based study analyzed the effect of pandemic on the personal and professional life of teachers, the devices they used to connect their students, level of internet accessibility, digital skills and competencies of teachers. Here impact of pandemic on the teachers' confidence level and their adaptability to new normal educational context. Major findings of the study revealed that impact was mild on the teachers of Udupi District and the main approach used by them was sending notes and recorded videos from various sources through Whatsapp. 14% of teachers visited student's homes and 175 of teachers never used virtual meetings during pandemic. 38% of teachers often evaluated their students using various methods. Teachers received average support from all the sources to continue teaching during pandemic. 15% of teachers received poor response whereas 455 of teachers got very good response during Covid -19.

INTRODUCTION

The Covid -19 impact was everywhere, which resulted in the closure of schools and other educational institutions. Though schools have closed students are attending their classes through various educational initiatives like online classrooms, radio programmers. This study aims to understand teachers ability to adapt in to new normal educational context and their digital literacy to carry out school activities.

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BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

This is a DESIGN BASED RESERCH study, was conducted under the guidance of TISS INDIA as per the instruction given by DSERT Bangalore Karnataka State.

DISTRICT PROFILE

Block name	Govt	Aided	unaided	Other dept	Total
Brahmavar	22	22	22	1	67
Byndoor	15	5	19	1	40
Karkal	27	13	23	2	65
Kundapur	20	7	17	1	45
Udupi	22	27	38	2	89
Total	106	74	119	7	306

There are 1443 PST, 185 GPT, 169 HM, 2 SPL and there are total 1931 teachers working in Udupi District.

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SURVEY RESPONDANTS PROFILE:

There are 965 teachers answered the tool used by the researcher. Respondents are teachers working in Government, Government Aided and unaided schools. Respondents are working in Lower Primary Schools, Higher Primary Schools and high Schools. More than 77% teachers are female and 84% teachers are working in Rural areas of Udupi District. 30% of teachers' age is above 50 years.

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TEACHERS DETAILS...

69% of teachers are belonging to OBC
 Respondents details based on professional qualification:

46% of respondents are having B.Ed., 23% of teachers having D.El.Ed.,M.A., 5% of teachers qualified T.C.H and 15% of teachers come under the category of other qualifications. Remaining 11% of teachers are having multiple and more than one qualifications such as M.A, M.Sc., B.Com., PGDCA,M.Ed.,B.A etc.

Respondents details based on School Category:

School category	Primary only (1-5)	Primary with upper primary (1-8)	Composite schools (1-10 or 1-12)	UP,HS,Sevondary (6-12) (9-12) (11-12)
%	10%	49%	26%	15%

Respondents details based on School Management:

64% of respondents working in Government schools, 19% of respondents working in Government aided schools and 17% of are working in Private Unaided Schools.

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Respondents categorisation based on Duration Of Teaching service:

Duration of service	Less than 5yrs	5-10 yrs.	10-20yrs	20 yrs. and more
%	10%	16%	31%	43%

Respondents categorisation based on Distance of their Residence from school:

There are 22% of respondents reside at the radiance of 5 km. 30% of respondents resides more than 30 km of distance from school. Distance of teacher’s residence from the school is major hindrance to carry out teaching during pandemic.

Respondents categorisation based on Mode of transport:

Mode of transport	Public	Private	Own vehicle	On foot
%	42%	13%	36%	09%

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SECTION TWO

IMPACT OF PANDAMIC; ACCESS AND CONNECTIVITY ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Introduction

In this section researcher analysed the impact of COVID-19 on the overall life of the teachers ,various strategies used by the teachers to get access to their students, mode of connectivity, level of competencies, level of digital skills possessed by the teachers before pandemic and level of confidence.

SECTION-2

14) Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic Access and Connectivity

Personal and professional Impact:

Personal and professional Impact of Covid -19 pandemic and lockdowns	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Covid -19 infections you/family members	642	225	80
Other health issues affected your ability to work during lockdown	562	306	93
Domestic matter affected to your work during lockdown	483	371	113
Financial matter affected to your ability to work during lockdown	453	337	177

15) Devices that you own and use for work

135 teachers i.e. 13.9% are having Computer Laptop /Desktop of their own for work. 0.62% teachers are having tablets. Majority of respondent’s i.e.85.2%.used their mobile smart phones to work.

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Devices that you own and use for work

16) Internet Connectivity

36 teachers i.e. 3.7% are having Broadband internet connectivity, 22.3% teachers used Mobile Data more than 1GB per day and 47.8% used less than 1GB per day. For 6.3% teachers there was Poor or No internet connectivity which reveals that 61 teachers never used devices throughout the pandemic period to access students connectivity.

17) Digital skills and competencies – confidence level.

Digital skills and competencies	Low	low	Average	High	High
Using Microsoft and similar office documents	188	296	424	49	10
Using Google forms Using video meetings	160	304	426	65	12
Using video meetings	120	287	462	77	21
Using browsers to access internet	114	256	440	110	47
Using Edtech and communication tools to teach	321	357	242	38	9

17.1 Using Microsoft and similar office documents

Level of digital skills and competencies and confidence level to use technology among teachers of Udupi District is an Average. Only 1% of teachers are having high Digital skills and competencies where as 19.4% teachers are having very low ability to use Microsoft and similar office Documents.

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17.2 Using Google forms

By analysing the data it was found that 44% of teachers were using Google forms on an Average basis and only 1% of teachers were used Google forms and having High ability use Google forms for different purposes.

17.3 Using video meetings(Googlemet,WebEx,Zoometc)

48% of respondents were using video meetings in an average level where as 12% of respondents were having very low ability to use video meetings shows low level of digital skills and competencies among teachers of Udupi district.

17.4 Using browsers to access Information

Only 46% of respondents are able to use browsers to access internet for information. 5% of teachers are having high ability use browsers and 12% of teachers are having very low level of ability to access internet for information

17.5 Using education Edtech and communication tools

After analysing the data it was found that only 25% of teachers are having average ability to use Edtech and communication tools like Geogebra, Cahoot, Padlet etc..

SECTION THREE TEACHING DURING THE PANDEMIC

18 The approaches used to teach during the pandemic

Here researcher tried to analyse the approaches used by teachers to teach during pandemic.

57% of teachers used Whatsapp for various purposes such as sending notes and exercises. 28% of teachers used slides/videos from other sources.25% of teachers used Recorded lectures to keep the students in continuous learning. Result also reveals that only 5% of teachers don't know to use Whatsapp. Only 8% of teachers used Google forms for assessments often, where as 38% of teachers were never used Google forms for assessment. Another important result found was 47% of teachers never prepared and used Power point presentation.

35% of teachers used recorded lectures using black or white boards during lockdown. After analysing the result it is evident that majority of teachers in Udupi District were used Watsapp for various educational purposes. This result also shows that teachers of Udupi District are having

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minimum digital skills and require more support on ICT.

19 The main issues faced while teaching during the pandemic

Here Researcher tried to understand the teachers ability to use the devices, availability of internet connectivity, maintenance of students attendance and students access to text books and other materials etc.

The main issues faced while teaching during the pandemic

The main issue I faced while teaching during the pandemic	Never	Rarely	Sometime	Often
Availability of devices	142	336	370	119
Availability of good internet connectivity	118	293	406	150
Ability to use the devices well	97	311	447	112
Ability to use appa/toola for online class	119	345	367	136
Time required for online class	200	287	361	119
Time table constraints	69	109	170	54
Availability of e-resources in Kannada	173	334	352	108
Students attendance	115	271	376	199
Attention and response from students	91	259	431	186
Students access to textbooks and other materials	152	230	346	239

19.1 The availability of devices and ability to use devices

12% of respondents devices are available and for 15% of respondents devices never available.

It was 12% of respondents were often able to use the devices well where as 10% of respondents never able to use the devices.

19.2 The availability of good internet connectivity

For only 16% Of teachers' internet connectivity was often available but for 12% of teachers internet connectivity unavailable. For 42% of teachers only sometimes and for 30% of teachers, internet was available rarely.

19.3 The ability to use the tools and apps

14% of teachers are able to use online tools and apps well where as 12% of teachers had no ability to use the online tools and apps for online classes.

19.4 The time required for lesson preparation

12% of teachers often faced issues with the time required for lesson preparation for online teaching,. 21% teachers never faced any issues and 37% of teachers faced issues sometimes and 30% of teachers rarely faced issues related to time

19.5 Availability of suitable E-resources in Kannada

For 18% of teachers Kannada e-resources were not available where as 11% of teachers always used

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Kannada e-resources. 36% of teachers used Kannada e-resources sometimes and 35% of teachers used it very rarely.

19.6 Availability of suitable E-resources in Kannada

19% of teachers often and 9% of teachers never faced any issues related to the attention and response of students

19.7 Students access to textbook and other material

16% of teachers never, 24% of teachers often, 36% of teachers sometimes and 24% of teachers rarely faced issues related students access to textbooks and other materials

20.0 The ways in which I connected with my students

In this section Researcher tried to find out how often teachers tried to keep in contact with their students for various reasons.

The ways in which teachers connected with their students

Ways of connection with students	Never	rarely	Sometimes	Often
Virtual meeting	162	220	374	211
Whatsapp and messaging app	20	86	268	593
In person inschool	184	350	350	83
Made home visit	147	297	391	132

20.1 Through virtual meetings

21% of teachers often, 17% of teachers never, 23% of teachers rarely and 39% of teachers sometimes in virtual contact with their students. Which shows majority of teachers are not relied on only virtual meeting.

20.2 Through Whatsapp and Messaging apps on Mobile

61% of teachers used Whatsapp more often but 2% of teachers never used Whatsapp. 9% of teachers rarely and 28% of teachers used it sometimes to maintain contact with students. Result shows that majority of teachers in Udupi District used Whatsapp for various educational purposes.

20.3 In person in school

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Only 9% of respondents went in person to school to contact their students. 19% of respondents never went in person to school during lockdown. 36% of teachers went very rarely and 36% of teachers went some times to school to meet their students.

20.4 Made home visits

14% teachers made home visits and 15% of teachers never made home visits.

21.0 The ways in which I was able to assess student’s learning

Researcher was intended to know if assessment was done, how often teachers assessed their student’s learning and what were the methods used for assessments.

Ways in which I was able to assess students learning	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
Observations and responses in live classes	19%	28%	36%	17%
Online quizzes using Google form and other tools	25%	35%	30%	10%
Phone calls and other verbal interactions	3%	13%	39%	45%
Written answers to test and assignments	3%	15%	44%	38%
Pear evaluations by students	17%	27%	39%	17%

21.1. Observations and responses in live classes

Total 17% of teachers often and 19% of teachers assessed their students by observing responses during live classes. 28% of teachers very rarely and 36% of teachers observed responses for sometimes in live classes.

21.2 Online quizzes using Google forms and other tools

10% of teachers have often conducted online quiz using Google form and 25% of teachers never conducted assessment by conducting online quiz using Google forms.

21.3 Phone calls and other verbal interactions

45% Of teachers are often, 3% of teachers never, 39% teachers sometimes and 13% of teachers

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rarely assessed their students through phone call and other verbal interactions.

Type of support to continue teaching duty during Covid-19	Very poor	Poor	Average	Good	Very good
Training before pandemic	5%	21%	37%	30%	7%
Training during pandemic	8%	29%	32%	26%	5%
Access to device	6%	30%	35%	25%	4%
Support for internet connectivity	6%	31%	36%	23%	4%
Recourses and tools for online teaching	7%	28%	36%	24%	5%

21.4 Written answers to test and other assignments

38% of respondents often, 3% of teachers never, 15% of teachers rarely and 44% of teachers assessed sometimes their students on written test and other assignments.

21.5 Peer evaluation by students

17% of teachers used peer assessment technique to assess their student’s learning and 17% of teachers never used this technique, 27% of teachers used this technique rarely and 39% of teachers used this technique some times.

22.0 The types of support I received to continue my teaching duty during covid-19

Here Researcher tried to find out the types of support received by teachers from various ends to carryout educational activities during Covid-19 pandemic.

22.1 Training/ professional development before pandemic/lockdown

7% of teachers received very good, 5% teachers received very poor training/professional development support & 21%of teachers received poor and 30% of teachers received good training/professional support before pandemic to continue their duty during Covid-19.

22.2.Training/ professional development during pandemic/lockdown 5% of teachers received very good, 8% of teachers received very poor, 29%of teachers received poor, 32% of teachers received average and 26% of teachers received good professional support during lockdown to continue their duty.

22.3.Access to devices

Only 4% of teachers had good access to devices and 6% of teachers had very poor access to devices.

22.4.Support for internet connectivity

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Here only 4% teachers received very good internet connectivity support. 6% of teachers had very poor internet connectivity support. 36% of teachers had average and 23% of teachers received good internet connectivity support to continue their teaching duty during Covid-19 pandemic/lockdown.

22.5. Resources and Tools for online teaching

Only 5% of teachers received very good and 7% of teachers received very poor resources and tools for online teaching. 36% of teachers received average resources and tools for online teaching.

23.0 Levels of support received from

Researcher tried to find out the support received from various ends such as family, colleagues, school heads, department, parents of students and community.

Levels of support received from	Very poor	Poor	Average	Good	Very good
Family	11	102	289	369	196
Colleagues	11	74	279	403	200
HM	16	63	266	383	239
Department	27	78	259	417	186
Students	17	138	315	362	135
Parents	19	172	296	361	119
Community	76	218	279	312	82

369 teachers got good, 196 teachers received very good support but only 102 teachers got poor support from the family. 403 teachers received good and 200 teachers received very good support from colleagues shows the co-ordination between teachers, and only 74 teachers received poor support from colleagues. 383 teachers received good, 239 teachers received very good support and 266 teachers received average support from schools heads shows the combined effort and co-ordination between teachers.

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417 teachers received good support from department and 362 teachers received good support from students and 361 teachers received good support from parents of the students and 312 teachers got good support from community. This result shows there was no external pressure and hindrance for teachers to carry out teaching work by adapting online during covid-19 pandemic.

From 138 students, 172 parents and 218 local community teachers received poor support to work during pandemic. Causes for non-cooperation may be poor network, unavailability of gadgets needed for online classes and fear of pandemic.

24.0 My opinion about teaching during the pandemic

My opinion about teaching during pandemic	Very poor	Poor	Average	Good	Very good
Response of students	15	260	361	286	45
Students academic learning	20	303	388	235	21
Students non-academic learning and development	35	331	384	191	26
Students emotional well being	39	263	390	257	18
Assessment of student learning	16	263	384	278	26
Feedback to students	12	233	391	295	36

24.1 Response 260 students was poor, 361 students response was average and 286 was good, where 260 students response were poor.

24.2 Students' academic learning was poor for 303 teachers, average for 388 teachers, and good for 235 teachers. This statistics reveals that the learning of students during pandemic was not as expected.

24.3 Student's non-academic learning and development was poor for 303 teachers, average for 384 teachers and good for 191 teachers which reveals that the overall development of students during

Covid- 19 pandemic was hindered and not up to the mark.

24.4 Students emotional wellbeing was average for 390 teachers, poor for 263 teachers and good for 257 teachers which shows the need students to work on their emotional wellbeing after school are open.

24.5 When students are assessed after teaching it was found good for 278 teachers average for 384 teachers and poor for 263 teachers shows the need for plan of action to improve students’ abilities as whole

24.5 Feedback received by the students during Covid -19 pandemic was poor for 233 teachers, average for 391, good for 295 students. Constructive feedback was the need of the hour.

CHAPTER FOUR SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

4.0.0 MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

- After having analysed the data assess the Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on school education of Udupi District the Researcher has come to the conclusion that the school education in Udupi district was greatly affected by COVID-19 pandemic.
- Pace of education was slow. Majority of teachers’ i.e.77% teachers working in the district are female teachers and only 22.9 are male teachers.
- More than 58% of teachers are above 40 years of age and above 69% are belonging to OBC category.
- The reason for slow pace of education was majority of schools situated in rural areas and having poor network connection or no network connection.
- Schools are 100% co-education and majority of schools i.e.49% are upper primary schools. There are 59% of schools are government schools and remaining constitutes both Aided and Unaided.
- After analysing the data it was evident that teachers in primary and upper primary schools teach more than one subjects affected the pace and effectiveness
- Only 5% of teachers are residing at the radiance of 5 km from the school and 30% of teachers must travel more 40 km daily affected the education.
- More than 40% of teachers travel by public transport and there was unavailability of public transport during COVID-19 pandemic was the major reason for slow pace of school education in Udupi District.
 - Personal and professional impact of COVID-19 was not major. Less than 50% teachers affected mildly by COVID-19 pandemic. Only 9% of teacher’s families were severely affected and COVID-19 pandemic affected 9% of teachers professionally. But 18% of teachers financially affected.
 - Mobile phone was the popular gadget used during COVID-19 for various educational purposes.
 - It was evident that only 4% of teachers connected broad band and 6% of teachers are out of network area. Network issue had an impact on school education during pandemic.
 - Analysis of data revealed that the digital competencies of teachers and ability to use digital skills are poor. Teachers having very high abilities to use digital skills are only 1%.
 - The major approaches used by the teaches of Udupi District during COVID-19 pandemic

to carry on the school education were sending notes and exercises via whatsapp, sending videos from other sources and recorded lecture. Modern live lectures, discussions and debate, Google forms for evaluation are not popular.

- Availability of gadgets and ability to use the gadgets was another constraint among teachers. The teachers faced multiple aspects during teaching such as students’ attendance, unavailability of time to prepare lesson and inability to use apps and tools for online classes.
- Watsapp and other messaging apps were popular among the teachers of Udupi district. Only 21% of teachers were often connected where as 17% of teachers never used virtual meetings.9% of teachers often met their students in the schools where as 19% of teachers never met their students during COVID-19 lockdown.
- 45% of teachers often connected their students by phone calls where as 3% of teachers never connected. 38% teachers often assessed students written answers where as 35% of teachers never assessed students written answers.
- Only 10% of teachers used Google forms and online quizzes for evaluation.
- Only 4% of teachers of Udupi district had access to devices and internet often
- 5% of teachers received very good professional development during lockdown.
- Availably of resources and tools was poor in 7% of teachers and very good resource support was available for only 5% of teaches.

4.2.0 IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Department should give Continuous guidance and mentoring to the performance of the teachers.
- ITC training must be given to the lower and upper primary school teachers.
- Department should give special training to the teachers to use technology
- Training must be given by the department to use advanced apps and tools teacher from each school must be attending this training.

4.3.0 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- Some items in the Research Tool it may not be applicable for all the regions..
- The tool used by the researcher is not standardised to find out the exact impact of covid-19 pandemic.
